

PUZZLING THROUGH THE PIECES TOGETHER: DEVELOPING THE PRESERVATION SERVICE MODEL FOR A NATIONAL REPOSITORY SERVICE

Julie Shi

*Scholars Portal
Canada*

julie@scholarsportal.info

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1242-1112>

Julia Gilmore

*Scholars Portal
Canada*

julia@scholarsportal.info

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5843-5238>

Abstract – Institutional repositories (IRs) house a significant record of unique academic works. Preserving these materials is vital to ensure ongoing access and usability, however there are several obstacles for preservation in the IR context. This paper outlines how the preservation puzzle is being approached by Scholaris, a new Canadian shared IR service that aims to support the open discovery, management, sharing, and preservation of Canadian scholarship. The service is being developed through an Early Adopter Program coordinated by Scholars Portal at the University of Toronto Libraries and expert groups facilitated by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries. This includes the Scholaris Digital Preservation Expert Group, which is lending support to create the digital preservation offering for the service. Beginning with an overview of digital preservation in the IR context and the Canadian landscape that led to the formation of Scholaris, the authors outline the goals and ongoing work of the expert group and reflect on challenges and lessons learned so far.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Institutional repositories (IRs) house a significant record of unique works created by our academic communities over time. Preserving this information for future access and use is therefore vital for IRs. IR programs face myriad challenges with preservation, however, from determining scope and establishing a

common understanding of digital preservation to creating a preservation strategy. With the recent launch of a national IR service, the Canadian IR community is exploring a collaborative approach to puzzling through these challenges together.

Scholaris is a national, opt-in, shared IR service launched in Canada in 2023. Development of the service is being led by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries (CARL), which represents 27 university libraries and three federal libraries in Canada, and Scholars Portal, the technical infrastructure department of the Ontario Council of University Libraries (OCUL) consortium. Scholars Portal was formed in 2002 to provide shared technology services to OCUL members and has recently expanded its services to academic and cultural heritage organizations across Canada. Scholars Portal is hosted by the University of Toronto Libraries (UTL). Service development is also informed by community-based expert groups for key areas in IR management. This includes the Scholaris Digital Preservation Expert Group (S-DPEG), which provides guidance and recommendations on digital preservation planning requirements and pathways.

This paper begins by looking at the preservation landscape for IRs and the specific Canadian context that led to the creation of Scholaris. The authors then introduce the scope and work of S-DPEG and conclude with reflections on challenges and lessons learned to date.

II. DIGITAL PRESERVATION AND INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES

Digital preservation has been part of IR conversations in North America since they began around the early 2000s. Preservation is central to Lynch's oft-cited definition of an institutional repository as "an organizational commitment to the stewardship of... digital materials, including long-term preservation where appropriate, as well as organization and access or distribution" [1, p. 2]. The practical need for preservation practices to achieve the latter objectives of organization and access for the long term is clear.

This is especially the case as IRs increasingly receive born digital materials, which bear higher risks in the absence of analogue originals. This risk increases when the deposited items are official versions, as is the case at many institutions for electronic theses and dissertations (ETDs) [2], [3]. IRs also accept non-ETD content, such as preprints, audio recordings, and teaching materials, that may not be published or preserved elsewhere. This range of content and media types makes establishing standardized workflows and sufficient controls over formats, metadata, and rights all the more challenging but crucial [2], [4]. Importantly, when an institution establishes an IR, it is not only "accepting risks" [1, p. 6] associated with ensuring the integrity and authenticity of the works it stewards [3]. It is also "making promises" and "creating new expectations" that the academic community can trust the IR and, by extension, the institution to properly preserve and provide access to those works over time [1, p. 6]. Keeping such promises is especially critical when "depositors may expect or assume long-term preservation when they deposit" [5, p. 270]. Faculty at 17 Carnegie universities in the mid-2000s shared that a key reason for low engagement with the repository was a lack of trust in IRs to provide long-term access to deposited works [6, p. 251].

Trends in the published literature suggest that while IRs recognize the importance of preservation, relatively few have policies and practices in place [7]–[10]. Momentum around preservation and curation stalled in early IR discussions due to tensions around the purpose and scope of IRs [7]. The area only regained steam after 2010 [11], with particular focus on preservation considerations for ETDs [2], [4]. These tensions and the deprioritization of preservation may be attributed to two dynamics. The

first refers to the diverging views of IRs as critical infrastructure for shifting to open access and competing with traditional publishers [12], compared to IRs as complementary publishing spaces for managing, sharing, and preserving works that had previously been unavailable to the public [1]. As such, "the importance given to the preservation of repository content will vary with each institution" [12, p. 37]. These views continue to shape the IR discourse [17]. The second dynamic relates to the unexpected struggles that libraries have continued to face to establish IRs as trustworthy and attractive places for faculty to deposit their work. This has led many to set looser file format and metadata requirements, which has simplified the deposit process but increased preservation challenges [5], [14]. These dynamics likely contributed to preoccupations with dissemination and access, outreach, and platform customizations to ensure IR programs survived [15]. Coupled with limited staffing and technical expertise, preservation was consequently sidelined.

When preservation for IRs does appear in the literature, discussions tend to focus on either the forest or the trees. The former secures high-level commitments through policies or mandates but lacks a corresponding implementation plan [8], [11]. In the latter more common framing, preservation is seen as a primarily technical issue, with discussions of metadata, rights, and file formats typically extending only as far as deposit [7], [14], [16]. Versioning is occasionally seen as a post-deposit preservation concern [2]. This technical focus may be due to features in various IR systems that are commonly associated with preservation, such as format identification, checksum generation, and preservation metadata support [16], [17]. For some, these features represent the extent of preservation activities [2], [8]. File formats, in particular, have received significant attention. While many IRs have format guidelines (often copying the defaults provided by the IR platform [17], [18]), far fewer have a formal preservation policy [14], [17]. A 2015 survey of 34 Swedish IRs found that around 70% of respondents provided format guidance in some form, yet 60% were unsure of the long-term plans for their repositories or the files received [17].

As vehicles for discovery and access, IRs are not designed to achieve preservation goals [2]. This is somewhat at odds with the depiction of IRs, often on

platform or library websites, as all-in-one access and preservation solutions. Preservation is also not merely a technical problem, and “well designed institutional repositories will separate system operation from curatorial and policy control” [1, p. 7]. Needs assessments, policies, and long-term planning are critical for building preservation capacity and ensuring the stability of the IR [5], [6]. Yet, in 2017, Plutchak reflected, “I think most people who manage institutional repositories view them as long-term preservation vehicles. They assume that the material that they put in is there permanently” [13, p. 34].

III. THE CANADIAN CONTEXT

A. *A Highlight Reel of IRs in Canada*

Academic libraries in Canada have been engaging with IRs since at least 2003. That year, CARL adopted a position statement supporting the “systematic archiving of, and access to digital research output of Canadian academic organizations into [sic] institutional repositories” [19]. This statement followed the launch of the CARL Institutional Repositories Project, which supported members implementing IRs by “monitoring the development of individual projects and facilitat[ing] exchange of best practices and lessons learned” [18, p. 166]. A survey of members in 2005 found that institutions needed more guidance to understand digital preservation in particular and how to apply best practices in IRs. Regional Canadian library consortia explored shared IR services through the early 2010s, including the CAIRN network in the Atlantic region [20], the Arca repository service for BC Electronic Library Network members [21], and ÉDUQ for Québécois colleges [22]. In addition to lightening the load for individual institutions through resource and knowledge sharing, these services supported institutions with responding to open access mandates introduced in 2015 by the Tri-Agency federal funding bodies that required funded researchers to deposit publications that were not immediately open access into an institutional or disciplinary repository [23].

Beginning in 2018, the state of the Canadian repository landscape (IR and otherwise) has been documented through an inventory of Canadian repositories that the community is invited to update on an annual basis. This initiative was started by the CARL Open Repositories Working Group (ORWG) to gain a better understanding of repository use and

infrastructure across the country [24]. By the early 2020s, the inventory included around 200 repositories, with many hosted and managed locally by institutions. More recently, CARL and OCUL heard from their respective communities that inadequate staffing and a lack of technical expertise were significant challenges for running IRs. The findings from the 2005 CARL survey still rang true, as IR teams continued to express interest in digital preservation but uncertainty about how to apply it in their context. Strong interest in community solutions was also expressed, and CARL and OCUL independently assessed the feasibility and opportunities of shared IR infrastructure. Both assessments concluded that a shared model could provide economies of scale, centralized technical support, and collective resource development, leading to more sustainable IR programs. CARL and OCUL and UTL thus agreed to share resources and expertise to collaborate on a hosted national repository service.

B. *Introducing Scholaris*

Scholaris [25] is a new national, opt-in shared IR service, providing scalable infrastructure, technical expertise, and community networks to support open discovery, management, sharing, and preservation of Canadian scholarship. Following a pilot project that started in 2023 with two OCUL institutions, Scholaris transitioned to a cohort-based Early Adopters program in April 2024. The program currently has over 20 subscribing institutions from across Canada with the majority now live on the Scholaris infrastructure. The service uses the DSpace open-source repository software and is hosted and managed by Scholars Portal at UTL. Scholars Portal is coordinating the Early Adopter Program, while CARL is leading the development of a sustainable governance and financial model for Scholaris through the Shared Repository Infrastructure Advisory Committee. Technical and community infrastructure are foundational to the development of Scholaris. Alongside the technical requirements for delivering an efficient and scalable service, developing community infrastructure is critical to building a service that serves the needs of the Canadian IR community and provides opportunities for alignment with international initiatives and best practices. To complement input from Early Adopters and further foster a culture of community-driven service development, CARL established three Network of Experts groups to identify best practices

and provide recommendations in critical areas of IR management: metadata and discovery, ETDs, and digital preservation. These expert groups are coordinated by the CARL Visiting Program Officer for the service and include representation from the Scholars Portal team.

IV. THE SCHOLARIS PRESERVATION PUZZLE

C. *Designing the Puzzle*

The Scholaris Digital Preservation Expert Group (S-DPEG) convened in August 2024. The group is charged with providing the Scholaris service team with recommendations, guidance, and advice on digital preservation planning, requirements, and pathways to (1) support the longevity of Scholaris as a service, and (2) ensure preservation supports and offerings reflect the needs, priorities, and capacity of subscribing institutions. Emphasis was also placed on developing a common understanding of digital preservation in the IR context and ensuring that the preservation service offering or roadmap for Scholaris can be integrated as seamlessly as possible with wider library infrastructure.

A call for membership was shared in late June 2024 and was open to staff from any institutions migrating or planning to migrate to Scholaris. Prior digital preservation knowledge or experience was not required, to ensure a range of perspectives, expectations, and concerns could be heard. Digital preservation and scholarly communications roles are evenly represented among the 10 members. This includes the authors as the Scholars Portal Digital Preservation Librarian (S-DPEG chair) and Digital Projects Librarian (Scholaris service lead and S-DPEG *ex officio* representative), who liaise between the group and the Scholaris service team and map discussions to service development. The other members provide valuable insights from their institutional contexts and raise important considerations when designing a national service, including differences in institutional structures, sizes, and preservation readiness.

The expert group crafted a nine-point work plan to understand the state of digital preservation for IRs in Canada and explore avenues to connect preservation planning and IR management in the Scholaris context. Each piece is designed to support the service team, Scholaris subscribers, and/or the wider IR community. Taken together, these pieces

will form the Scholaris preservation puzzle and support taking a “preservation where possible” approach for both service provision and IR management. It is important to note that this puzzle is not intended to be a comprehensive preservation program or a prescriptive preservation approach for Scholaris subscribers, as “even within a consortium, individual institutions make their own choices about content and scope” [15, p. 5]. Instead, the puzzle is intended to offer approachable starting points for Scholaris as a service and a community.

A. *Preservation Pieces for the Service Provider*

The technical infrastructure for Scholaris consists of parallel, customizable instances of DSpace for each institution hosted on dedicated virtual machines on Scholars Portal servers with live storage on spinning disk and nightly backups to tape. The Digital Projects Librarian liaises with subscribing institutions to understand desired functionality and coordinates with two systems team members on technical developments. The complex nature of the infrastructure and growing uptake of the service make it critical to design Scholaris with an eye to the future.

1. *Features and Workflows*

S-DPEG’s work began by establishing a common grounding. As members were variously familiar with DSpace, technical jargon, and preservation topics, the group agreed that it was important for Scholaris to provide subscribers with *a clear understanding of DSpace features that support preservation* (item 1), and *straightforward workflows to enable further preservation work* (item 2) to ensure a clear and digestible scope for the preservation offering.

Work by the ORWG in 2019 addressed a similar goal to advance “a common understanding of basic digital preservation requirements and functionality” [16, p. 2] in the IR context. Reviewing common IR platforms, the ORWG described available features in each that could support bit-level preservation, preservation metadata, and data exports. Inspired by this effort, the co-authors reviewed the current DSpace documentation [26] to identify default and configurable features that could support preservation. When the authors shared an overview of their findings, group members expressed excitement but also a sense of overwhelm at the technical terminology. As such, the authors have

drafted a plain language guide to facilitate a baseline understanding of the DSpace features available in Scholaris and how they can be leveraged within a larger preservation program.

S-DPEG members who use DSpace and have preservation workflows in place also shared how various features are employed at their institutions. Current and prospective Scholaris subscribers also shared similar information with the Digital Projects Librarian during information calls and Early Adopter meetings. Workflows ranged from using the DSpace REST API [26, p. 480] and AIP Backup and Restore [26, p. 404] utility to transfer data to external preservation or storage systems, to using a vendor-modified version of the Replication Task Suite add-on [27] to export data for processing in Archivematica. This feedback greatly supported the authors in understanding use cases and considerations for each workflow, and framing preservation features in the guide.

These two work items also directly informed a third task *to determine what preservation supports could be offered within the Scholaris service model* (item 3). The group determined that two pathways should be explored: one to connect Scholaris with an institution's existing preservation infrastructure; and the other to integrate Scholaris with the broader Scholars Portal ecosystem, which includes the Permafrost hosted Archivematica service, and the Ontario Library Research Cloud preservation storage service. Members shared that an integrated, end-to-end Scholars Portal solution that addresses deposit through to preservation would allow institutions to focus on the nuts and bolts of preservation instead of on systems integrations. A subgroup was thus formed to define common use cases based on the scenarios shared, determine technical workflows and requirements for each, and translate the final set of use cases and workflows into a flexible and scalable service offering. Preference was given in the initial pathway to options that are in use, are of demonstrated interest, or leverage existing functionality, tools, or scripts. This has led the service team to its current investigations into the DSpace REST API and the Replication Task Suite plugin, the structure of DSpace's three export formats (the DSpace AIP, BagIt-based AIP, and the Simple Archive Format), and possible solutions for sharing data exports with institutions.

2. Risk Management

These technical supports are only valuable if Scholaris remains viable as a service. Another subgroup was therefore created *to develop a risk management matrix to support the service team with identifying, monitoring, and mitigating against risks to continued service delivery* (item 4). As a certified Trusted Digital Repository (TDR) for licensed journal articles [28], Scholars Portal is familiar with preservation and risk management strategies. The service team was therefore very receptive to this effort for Scholaris, for which S-DPEG is very grateful.

After reviewing various resources to understand common risk factors and frameworks [29]–[32], the subgroup unanimously agreed to reference the extensive list of risk classes and factors related to digital content and organizational and technological infrastructure in Pennock's CHARM model [31]. As Scholaris is not the steward of any specific deposits, the matrix emphasizes organizational and technological sustainability and gives less attention to content-specific risks. Fixity and overall access to the repository are considered under technology. Inspired by Schaefer's paper on adapting to climate change [33], the subgroup also added a category for environmental sustainability. Considerations for each risk class and factor are mapped to the recovery model [30], which provides a structure for outlining possible risk events, mitigation strategies, and recovery processes. As the Scholaris service team is the primary audience for this matrix, a spreadsheet was chosen as the most practical format for viewing and updating information. The spreadsheet was populated during a series of working meetings, and the service team and the Scholars Portal TDR risk analysis were consulted to better understand the technical infrastructure and identify possible alignments for mitigation and recovery. The matrix has been reviewed by S-DPEG and the service team for accuracy and feasibility and will continue to be reviewed on a regular basis.

A. Preservation Pieces for Subscribing Institutions

Preservation is of course more than just file formats and technical systems, and the heavy lifting of program and policy work must occur at the institutional level. As noted, however, preservation is not well established in the IR context. An information gathering subgroup was thus formed to help S-DPEG *develop a better sense of current digital preservation*

practices, capacity, and needs in the Canadian IR landscape (item 5). Findings from this subgroup are guiding the wider group's current work to *develop explainers for IR teams and end-users about digital preservation and Scholaris* (item 6) and *create a digital preservation toolkit for institutions with guidance on general preservation topics* (item 7). The metadata and discovery and ETD expert groups will also be consulted to ensure guidance is aligned.

1. Understanding the Landscape

The information gathering subgroup began with an initial search for policies published online by 34 Canadian institutions. This was not a comprehensive review, however a consistent commitment to the ongoing readability, usability, and discoverability of IR content was found in the 11 digital preservation and 26 IR policies identified. Various preservation activities were referenced, including fixity checks; format guidance and management strategies; collection, retention, and withdrawal guidelines; backup, storage, and security systems; and contingency plans. These activities did not appear consistently and were not always directed towards IR content, which suggests both awareness and gaps in preservation strategies. To learn more about preservation in practice, the subgroup developed a survey for the IR community with 21 questions on preservation-related platform functionality; current preservation practices, capacity, and systems; and challenges and opportunities for preservation in the IR context. The survey was created in Google Forms and shared through CARL and Scholaris channels. Responses were collected from February 10 to March 11, 2025, and 22 completed surveys were received from 20 institutions, 13 of which are current or potential Early Adopters and 16 of which are also represented in the environmental scan.

Overall, the results reveal a strong need for clarity around the relationship between digital preservation and IRs, the limitations of IR systems for preservation, and how to do preservation in the IR context. One respondent also expressed uncertainty about how Scholaris fit into the preservation picture given that preservation strategies vary significantly by institution. Less than half of respondents indicated that their institution has a preservation policy or strategy, which aligns with the findings of the earlier scan. Respondents reflected a greater awareness of technical preservation activities, particularly fixity checks, format management,

metadata, and versioning. A lack of expertise, staff, and resources, however, means most institutions either have limited or no preservation activities in place or rely on default platform or vendor support. While robust workflows were shared by a few respondents, one respondent noted that their institution is not immune to the above challenges as preservation is only one service of many involved in IR management. It is unsurprising, then, that many respondents expressed a strong desire for training opportunities to build local capacity for developing preservation programs and carrying out operational tasks. Respondents also requested guidance on best practices and standards for preservation in the IR context, as well as facilitation of a national community of practice. These and other topics identified by respondents represent key focus areas in the S-DPEG explainers and toolkit.

V. CONCLUSION

A. Next Steps: Connecting the Pieces

The preservation puzzle for materials managed in Scholaris is a complex one with many moving parts and pieces that have yet to be designed. Given the complexities of preservation and the wide range of institutional mandates and contexts, there will be no one-size-fits-all solution. *Defining roles and responsibilities for preservation* (item 8) and *developing a preservation policy for Scholaris* (item 9) are thus crucial next steps to establish a clear understanding of the preservation scope for Scholaris. In the service model, preservation is considered a shared responsibility between Scholars Portal as service provider and subscribers as the experts on their institutional context, user communities, and deposited collections. Applying the three-legged stool metaphor as a framework, responsibilities may be divided into technical infrastructure, organizational infrastructure, and resourcing [34].

Scholaris is committed to providing subscribers with technical infrastructure for IR management and support for preservation, however the service team is not embedded in institutional contexts. Librarians and staff at each institution are far better equipped to identify and respond to the needs of their respective communities and collections. Institutions must therefore design preservation strategies and workflows that suit their particular contexts and capacities. Institutions can then apply workflows and

features offered by Scholaris to support their preservation goals. Through its community infrastructure, Scholaris can also provide guidance to support community needs related to the organizational and resourcing legs of the stool.

B. Challenges and Lessons Learned

The work and findings of S-DPEG thus far confirm the discussions in the literature: the why of preservation is broadly understood, but the how of preservation in the IR context is not always clear and limited resources make it a low priority. When preservation is addressed, activities often focus on technical operations that rely on the default system functionality. Building a new national, library-based, and community-led infrastructure service offers many opportunities to re-prioritize preservation in the IR context and connect the forest to the trees by embedding preservation considerations in the service development and conversations with subscribers about IR management and operations.

This path is of course not seamless. The co-authors have found that the vast range of perspectives, expertise, and experiences within the S-DPEG and wider IR community can make it challenging to develop and maintain shared understandings of preservation for IRs and the roles that different parties and systems can play. Iterative and careful planning is also crucial to account for the diverse needs of institutions with different capacities and priorities, and to determine if, how, and to what extent Scholaris can respond to those needs. Over two decades of collaboration on shared infrastructure projects have fostered a deep sense of trust and respect between Scholars Portal and Canadian institutions though, and we are grateful for these long-standing relationships that allow us to share our knowledge, questions, and experiences to move towards common goals.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Julie Shi is the Digital Preservation Librarian at Scholars Portal and the chair of the Scholaris Digital Preservation Expert Group.

Julia Gilmore is the Digital Projects Librarian at Scholars Portal and an ex-officio member of the Scholaris Digital Preservation Expert Group.

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